

A Comparative Analysis of Deep Learning Mobile Networks on Marine Vessel Detection

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Abstract

Maritime vessel detection and classification is a challenging research domain in computer vision due to, for example, ever-changing weather patterns, tidal and seasonal variations. In recent years, deep learning or deep neural networks (DNN) have shown enormous potential in the field of computer vision and have steered us towards practical applications such as vessel identification and classification and so on. There have also been promising results in the accuracy of mobile network architectures to support the real time application of DNN’s in a maritime environment. However, there is a gap in the literature in the comparative evaluation of mobile DNN architectures in the maritime domain. This paper presents a comparison of three high-performing networks, each of different size, on marine vessel datasets for marine object detection and classification task. The performance matrices are analysed for model accuracy and speed. We observe that among the models evaluated on the Singapore Maritime Dataset (SMD)-plus, in terms of accuracy, yolo-v8 has the best performance.

Keywords: Marine Vessels, Machine Vision, Detection, Localization, Deep Learning

1 Introduction

Maritime vessels are one of the important modes of passenger, freight, and cargo transportation for the modern world. Additionally, these vessels are actively used for pleasure activities and sport. In 2020 alone, 230 million passengers embarked and disembarked European ports, and 3.3 billion tonnes of freight were handled [Eurostat, 2022]. This large-scale movement of people and goods presents additional challenges as the increase in these activities will, for example, likely correspond with an increase in human trafficking, illicit drug trafficking, and illegal goods smuggling. One relatively recent report shows that most of the cocaine seized in the EU is mainly transported by maritime shipping containers [Europole, 2022]. This underlines the increasing need for a reliable, and automated system to address these issues.

Deep learning is becoming a widely accepted technology in almost every domain, whether is it to predict protein structure from sequence data, develop intelligent driving agents, or in natural language settings [Jumper et. al, 2021] [Tom et. Al, 2020]. Additionally, these innovations are advancing rapidly with the emergence of advanced hardware and a bounty of data. From this perspective we can sense that the development in deep learning technology to be gradually shifting towards two distinct directions. One towards the development of larger models, to generalize to wider application settings, such as represented by the growth in parameters of large language models (LLMs) such as growth in GPT-3 to GPT-4 [Brown et al., 2020] [OpenAI, 2023]. While the other direction is towards miniaturised versions so that they can be effectively implemented on low resource devices for numerous real-world applications “on the edge”, using for instance a drone platform. As a result, in

recent years, there has been extensive research in smaller networks architectures, which balance a trade-off between model accuracy and latency [Wang et. al]. These smaller models have shown state-of-the-art results in many publicly available datasets including Pascal VOC, ImageNet, and MS-Coco. However, there has not been enough open-sourced dataset to test the robustness of these model beyond the scope of general object detection, face detection or similar. Even with the few existing datasets that are suitable for the task, they have not been properly assessed with the latest models, which have been reported to have better trade-off between model accuracy and the computational latency.

This study aims to address this gap and is motivated by the urge to apply novel technologies in addressing those problems. To this end, we analysed smaller but multiple high performing network architectures “out of the box” with the default parameter settings on a domain specific problem of sea-vessel detection and localization. This will allow us to compare models in terms of both accuracy and speed for real world application using a drone platform. The models that we evaluated are mobilenet-v3 (large) with SSDlite, yolo-v8 (large), and mobilenet-v3 (large) with FRCNN [Howard et. al, 2019] [Jocher et. al, 2023] [Ren et. al, 2015]. We analyse performance on the Singapore maritime dataset (SMD)-plus [Kim et. al, 2022]. In the remainder of this paper we focus on a brief review of research in publicly available maritime datasets, and a review of general object detection and maritime vessels detection. We then outline our experimental design before discussing results and opportunities for future research.

2 Related Work

Maritime Datasets: Although DNN based approaches have shown promising results in recent times, one of the key issues with them is the requirement of a large-scale ground truth training dataset. Research on maritime vessel detection has been largely affected due to the lack of annotated datasets. There are several datasets available in the public domain, but they are limited by their intended aim of image classification but not localisation as most of them lack bounding box annotation for object localisation. For example, the Seagull dataset has multi-spectrum images for research on maritime environments however these datasets are limited to vessel detection and are not suitable for vessel localisation without further annotating them [Marques et. al]. Similarly large-scale image datasets of maritime vessels [Gundogdu et. al, 2016] include over 100 vessels categories; however, they also do not include bounding box annotation. Other publicly available datasets include a marine obstacle detection dataset [Kristan et. al, 2015], which holds data for large and small obstacles but does not accommodate neither proper classification of vessels nor the annotation for object localisation. Additionally [Moosbauer et. al, 2019] [Zhang et. al, 2021] lays out references for other multiple sources of publicly available datasets but they are limited to a reduced set of categories of carrier/vessels and does not supply the large video segment.

The Singapore Maritime Dataset (SMD) [Prasad et al., 2016], however, provides larger multi-spectrum video segments with 10 different classes of sea-vessels. The data are classified in two distinct categories as onshore data and onboard data. Onboard data is collected using a vision sensor mounted on vessels as they move along Singaporean ports, while the onshore data is collected from the seashore. SMD- plus [Kim et. al, 2022] is a refined version of SMD through the addition of annotation, tightening of the bounding boxes, and the classes are reduced to 7 from the original 10 in SMD. The SMD includes annotation for both object detection and classification. It includes both class labels and bounding boxes annotation for object localization. The dataset can be obtained from the link in its original paper [Kim et. al, 2022] (<https://github.com/kjunhwa/SMD-Plus>). The github link also provides reference to the original dataset by Prasad et. al. Figure 1 shows samples from SMD-plus video clips. We can see that the dataset is quite varied given the fact that it includes videos from different weather conditions.

Figure-1: SMD-plus dataset samples

Sea-vessel detection: There has been much research in computer vision and several approaches have been investigated for detection, classification, and localization of marine objects. For example, [Dawkins et. al, 2014] uses the feature engineering technique to identify maritime objects from the ocean, which is further extended by [Maire et. al, 2013] in marine mammals' detection based on images collected in aerial surveys. In marine object detection we can see multiple works in horizon detection [Prasad et al., 2018] [Teutsch & Krüger, 2010] as a part of pre-processing. Prasad et. al with their SMD dataset evaluate multiple methods for background reduction, however, such approaches might not be robust enough in the context of sea or coastal environments as background changes are abrupt and very common in such a context [Moosbauer et. al, 2019]. Several other techniques such as Hidden Markov Models and Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM) have been used to overcome such issues [Westall et. al, 2009] [Frost & Tapamo, 2013], but deep learning approaches seem to be successful in more complex object detection and segmentation problems.

There have been few attempts at maritime object detection and classification using smaller architectures in deep learning. Most of those works have assessed multiple variants of yolo [Leela et. Al, 2020] [Yan et. Al, 2022]. However, we rarely observe the evaluation of these models with other variations like widely popular mobile-net variations or similar ones. For example, [Kim et. al, 2022] in their publication have evaluated SMD-plus with yolo-v5 and further used copy-paste technique to improve the accuracy of the model, however, it does not provide any overview of the speed and accuracy of the model in real-time scenarios. Similarly [Moosbauer et. al, 2019] has benchmarked SMD on two different state-of-the-art models, Faster-RCNN and Mask-RCNN, and has introduced additional techniques such as multiscale combinatorial grouping to generate pixel-wise segmentation from bounding box information but again the paper lacks comparison of those models with other architectures. Likewise [Tian et al., 2021] [Sun et al., 2022] have focused their research on either object classification, detection, or segmentation but it also lacks the analysis with models having fewer parameters. A recent paper by [Munin et. al, 2023] has evaluated yolo-v8 on the dataset of only 624 images for 13 different vessels and has achieved impressive results with mAP@50 of 98.9% for the similar task of detection and classification, however, the result is based on a limited dataset which hardly seems to contain objects of smaller (pixel) size. Therefore, the contribution of this paper could be seen as an effort to bridge the gap such that it attempts to; (i) evaluate existing smaller networks models using the SMD-plus dataset and, ii) benchmark the performance on more constrained computing resources.

3 Experimental Setup

As mentioned in the preceding section we use the SMD-plus dataset to evaluate the models. The dataset is provided in two categories of onboard and onshore data. Fig-2 shows the distribution of video frames on those two categories. Clearly, it has a higher number of video frames from the onboard camera which is mounted on sea vessels while it was slowly moving around the Singaporean port. This is beneficial in terms of model training as these onboard videos have high degree of tidal oscillation which helps in creating variations in the dataset. Fig-3 shows the distribution of the number of objects on each class on SMD-plus dataset. We can clearly observe that dataset has a class imbalance problem, such that, the vessel/ship category has relatively higher number of objects associated with it of nearly 71%. Therefore, we train the model in two different settings, (i) *including all 7 classes* and, (ii) *with only 6 classes* by removing the vessel/ship category as we want to observe the effect of the imbalanced dataset on the overall result of the model. The dataset is provided as a raw video frame in *avi* format. We used a total of 51 video frames for training. From each video file we created image frames each with a sample of 5 frames. A total of 4377 frames were generated from the provided video file. We further randomly subsample images to train/validation sets by distributing them in a ratio of 7:3. Those 30% frames in the validation set were vital for better generalization of the model as they help in preventing model overfitting. We further added data-augmentation technique in the training framework to increase the robustness in the dataset. Basically, we only used horizontal flip for generating additional image frames.

Figure-2: Distribution of onshore and onboard video clips in SMD-plus dataset

Figure-3: Distribution of objects associated with classes on SMD-plus dataset

Models were trained in two different frameworks. Mobilenet-v3 with SSDlite was trained on TensorFlow while yolo and mobilenet-v3 with FRCNN version were trained on Pytorch. We consider these models because (i) they are among the state of art model architectures for edge platforms [Wang et. al, 2022] [Terven et. al, 2023] whose performance have not yet been evaluated together in domain specific sea-vessel detection and, (ii) the model includes smaller architecture (like mobile-net) to much complex versions like yolo-v8 and halfway sized mobilenet-v3 with FRCNN, these variation in parameters would enable us to examine co-relation in between size of the model and its accuracy if any. SSDlite is the lighter version of SSD architecture [Liu et al., 2016] which might not generalize sufficiently in the complex object detection task therefore, keeping the feature extractor same (mobilenet-v3) with multiple detectors would allow us to confirm if lighter feature extractor (model) with more complex detector produces any better results. As we wanted to observe the effect of parameter sizes in this small architecture, we consider experimenting with models with varying parameter sizes in a way that are large enough to better generalize in domain specific sea-vessels detection but relatively small enough to run efficiently in a real-time scenario on edge platforms. Fig-6 shows the size of those three models. We can observe from the figure that mobilenet-v3 is relatively smaller than the remaining two models, whereas yolo-v8 has the higher number of parameters. Training was performed using NVIDIA RTX 4090 GPU. For consistency

batch size were set to 16 and were trained for 100 epochs. The input size of the image was 640x640. In total, we conducted at least 6 different training instances; first half being the case where models were trained and evaluated on all 7 classes, and the remaining half was performed on 6 classes excluding vessels/ship category.

4 Results

The performance of the model has been quantified in terms of both average precision to evaluate the accuracy of the model, and a count of average frames per second to measure computational latency. As mentioned in the previous section, we apportioned our evaluation into two sets. In the first set, assessment was staged on the dataset with all class categories. The chart illustrated in Fig-4 shows the evaluation result in the form of mean average precision (mAP) [Padilla et. al]. The figure shows that the yolo-v8 has better accuracy in sea-vessel detection and localization problem in contrast to the other two models. It scores 0.82 mAP with intersection of union (IoU) in between 0 to 50 while the scores shrink to 0.52 while evaluating it with IoU between 50 to 90. Similarly, on the second set, vessels/ship categories were excluded, and assessment was done with only 6 classes. Fig-5 underlines the outcome and we can witness that the accuracy drops overall. Unlike yolo in previous cases, for 6 classes the accuracy of yolo drops, however it is still the best performer in overall evaluation. Likewise, in case of mobilenet-v3 with SSDlite detector accuracy seems consistent in both cases although there is a small fluctuation on the scores while comparing the result with 6 classes. Mobilenet-v3 with fernn detector has high mAP in comparison to the one with SSDlite but the score reduces while accessing it with 6 classes. Other interesting observations that can be made while evaluating Fig-4 and Fig-5 is that the accuracy in terms of average precision seems to increase as the complexity of the model increases. However, the observation does not correlate with the latter case.

The plot illustrated in Fig-6 demonstrates size verses speed performance of the models. Note that they were evaluated on an NVIDIA GPU RTX 3060Ti. As expected, we observed that the model with a smaller parameter size (mobilenet-v3-SSDlite) has the lowest latency with an average fps of 77. In contrast, yolo-v8 whose fps is recorded as 33 on average (with almost 47.5 million parameters) has the highest latency of the models examined. Mobilenet-v3 with the more complex FRCNN detector has similar inferencing speed to the SSDlite version.

Fig-4: Mean average precision of the models trained on SMD-plus with 7 classes. The black dotted line with star mark indicate result for mAP50 and the latter gray mark indicates result for mAP90

Fig-5: Mean average precision of the models trained on SMD-plus with 6 classes. In this case, we excluded vessels/ship class. The black dotted line with star mark indicate result for mAP50 and the latter gray mark indicates result for mAP90

5 Discussion and future work

One of the primary objectives of this evaluation was to identify the most accurate, but smaller, model to address the domain specific problem of marine vessel detection, which could be deployed on the edge. In so doing, we observe that in general yolo-v8 outperforms the two other models that were evaluated. During the experiment it was also observed that mobilenet-v3 with SSDlite was particularly good with smaller object detection, and yolo-v8 was better in detecting larger objects. However, further research is required to verify this outcome as the observations may be associated with the class imbalance issue. Another noticeable observation in this study is the imbalance of the data and its impact. As

more than two thirds of objects were associated with only a single class, we can see that there is a significant variation with the result of evaluation between only 6 classes (without the majority class) when compared with a dataset comprised of all 7 classes. The mAP significantly drops while the training was performed in only 6 classes. With half of the dataset, it might be possible that the number of datasets was simply not enough to allow model generalisation. Conversely, it might also be possible that the accuracy was elevated in case of all 7 classes since the number of majority class objects (vessel/ship) were far greater, and the detection of these object might have been better than other smaller objects such as sailing boats, buoys, or kayaks. In addition, we observe that the larger models (higher number of parameters) generalize well in sea-vessel detection, however the experiment excluding the majority class doesn't seem to enhance performance. Likewise, switching the detector of mobilenet-v3 with FRCNN does not clearly make any distinction on the result as the outcome varies significantly in between the cases.

There are multiple possible directions in which to continue this research into the future. For instance, since we are evaluating these models performances for time critical applications, detail analysis of evaluation on multiple edge platform is missing in this paper which is the immediate work that we are looking to accomplish going forward. Additionally, with the current experiment we can see that the dataset has been a major limitation as there is a huge difference in the ratio between the majority class objects and the others. Therefore, further exploration is needed in the data collection and curation so that a balanced dataset could be prepared for such domain specific problems. Another interesting direction could be to search the space of smaller architectures (network architecture search) using a neuro-evolutionary approach where an evolutionary algorithm is used to search network topologies with a view to find models having a better trade-off between accuracy and size. Likewise, we can see that some networks have very low computational latency and others have better accuracy, hence exploring a hybridisation between these networks would be another interesting area to explore in the future.

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Figure-6: Model size versus computational latency (evaluated on RTX 3060Ti GPU)

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